

A Study on the Impact and Dynamic Computer Studies for Women in Sivagangai District

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Abstract

Rural women's studies and social development is necessary for overall economic development of society and nation. Rural women are now highly update their knowledge through various type of studies specifically mainly they concentration on computer studies yet their entrepreneurial potential, managerial skill and socio-economic contribution remain largely neglected the institutional and policy framework for developing entrepreneurial skills, providing vocational education and training has widened the horizon for economic development of women. Economic empowerment of rural women will lead to the development of our country and it is very necessary to give keen attention over the empowerment of women in the rural areas for the real development of our country in all spheres. Women's entrepreneurship is important for women's position in society, and economic development of women will lead to development of family, community and country. It opens up new avenues for creating employment opportunities for women and men. The present paper focuses on parameters to be focused to enhance the entrepreneurial skill of rural women and in turn their empowerment.

Introduction

At a cost to both their own opportunities and society's capability to produce people with much-needed technical skills, women carry on to be under represented in computer science degree programs at both the UG degree and PG degree level in Sivagangai district. Even though some of the barriers that women face have their basics in cultural opportunity established well before the college level, we judge that education department can take effective steps to boost recruitment and preservation of women students.

During our society women enjoy an exclusive position and their donation to the Social development and improvement can never be denied. In generally all part of the globe their circumstances in structure the countrywide character is major their role to the society is multiple and they have got multifaceted personality as they play the role of mother, sister, wife and daughter through various stages of their life. In their role in various capacities they become a part of the society. In the current age in this new millennium they have exposed their brilliance in almost all fields and their contribution in political, civil & overall growth of a country is generally appreciated and accepted and they have proved be more week and are equal with men.

Despite all these, even today, a major chunk of women folk are deprived of the basic necessities of life and are creature considered as a deserted piece of the society. They have become fatality of the social set-up and sex-based unfairness continued to govern the society there by miserly them from all sort of facilities. They are treated unfavourably and the concept of equality and equal status has become myth for them. The recent and autonomous India realizing the inequality and prejudice against women has incorporates in the constitution, the Law of the land, several provisions which explicitly declare that women should be treated at par with men at the entire walks of life and there should be no discrimination and specific provisions are laid down for their up-development.

The Empowerment Concept

The perception of empowerment flows from that of authority. In the ordinary sense “Power is the capability to do anything”. In the social framework power can be considered “as the authority, right to command, right to govern or rule, capability to influence etc.,” empowerment plainly means the vesting of control where it does not exist, or exist poorly. It is a concept that does not merely concern personal characteristics but brings out a broader scrutiny of human rights and social righteousness. Empowerment has three elements:-

- Access to productive asset such as land, credit and technologies that can produce Income.
- Access to basic needs such as education, health services, water, fuel, shelter etc.
- Involvement in decision-making.

Barriers to Women in Computer Studies

Breathing barriers to women in undergraduate computer science programs have been all-inclusive in many previous reports, several of which are listed in the situation section or appear as reprints in this issue of Inroads. intelligence that we encircle found particularly useful include the revolutionary MIT “Barriers” report; the first extraordinary concern of Communications of the ACM devoted to women in computer science; Ellen Spertus’ report on the insufficiency of women in computer science; the study of female undergraduate enrolment in computer science and electrical engineering at MIT; the Computing Research Association study of employment and preservation of women graduate students, which is reprinted in this particular matter, and the book *Unlocking the Clubhouse* by Allan Fisher and Jane Margolis. The barrier themselves are not the main meeting point of this paper, which is disturbed with assessing the effectiveness of various strategies to increase the number of women undergraduates in computer science. Even so, designing effective solutions requires understanding the causal problems. Near a large extent, computer science departments face the same recruitment and retention problems that affect other engineering disciplines.

These common problems—patterns of prejudiced behaviour that create an uncooperative classroom environment, gender linked differences in how students assess their own performance, the scarcity of role models, and the be short of a sufficient critical mass to keep going supportive peer communities—are all critically important in computer science. There are, however, other, more specific problems that seem exclusive to or particularly pronounced in computer science, including the following:

- The level of computing practice that students have past to college differs markedly with gender.
- The extraordinary flexibility of software makes it easier to incorporate social biases in the design of computing systems.
- The traditions that develop around computer science departments are often unattractive to women.

These factors all have a negative impact on recruitment and retention of women.
Computer Bachelor's degrees women's strength in Sivagangai District

Data sources: NSF and Department of Computer Education

The Importance of Numbers

One of the major barriers to women's sharing in computer science is the intricacy of creating a critical mass of women within an organization. To a large scope, the ability to develop such an essential gathering is a function of the number of women available to become part of that community. Producing more women with computer science degrees is also central over the longer term, because it increases the group of skilled women who can serve as mentors for future generations. Lying on a national level, statistics about the production of undergraduate degrees put forward that increasing the total number of students has a correlated outcome not only on the number of women, but on their percentage as well. Figure 1, for example, illustrates the number of undergraduate degrees given to men and women from 1970 to 2000. The blueprint of the overall curve from 1970 to 1995 is memorable to most computer science educators. After growing gruffly in the 1970's and early 1980's, the number of undergraduate degrees in computer science—for both women and men—declined sharply for several years before beginning to level out in the mid-1990s. However, as the line superimposed on the bar graph indicates, the sliding trend was sharper for women. The percentage of degrees awarded to women tends to track the total number of computer science degrees.

A startling number of writer's quality the decline to a downturn in business demand, even with the fact that the decline that led to such a downturn occurred a number of years after the number of computer science graduates began to diminish. Really, the refuse in the number of computer science degrees was basically the result of unambiguous steps taken by academic institutions to decrease computer science enrolments when it became impracticable to take on enough faculties to meet the demand. These steps included, for example, striking more strict requirements for admission to the major, adding new required courses in mathematics, and transforming opening courses into filters designed to limit entry into the field. Such strategies have a disproportionately negative effect on enrolment by women and minorities. This past blueprint has become gradually more related in the last few years, when the numbers of computer science graduates has again begun to increase sharply. Although the data from 1997 and 1998 show a declining percentage of women in the face of increasing enrolments, both the numbers and percentage of women have risen in 1999 and 2000. The fact that the growth in participation by women lags somewhat behind the increase in enrolment is predominantly interesting when you take it together with the fact that is a resultant lag in the growth pattern during the enormous enrolment boom in the mid-1980s, when the percentage of women started to reject a couple of years before the overall enrolments had hit their peak.

Why Aren't More Women Involved In Computer Studies?

Earlier to the crack of dawn of the home computer in the early 1980s, greatly more women undertake computer science degrees. According to the National Centre for Education Statistics, in the academic year 1984-1985 women joined for nearly 37 percentages of all computer science UG students. This quantity progressively dropped as the prevalent use of own computers became very common. One of the 1985 statement on the daily usage of personal computers within the residence found that men were both far more likely to use a computer, and to use it for extra hours per week than women. Only 29% of men not reported with a computer on a weekly basis, compared to 55% of females surveyed. Starting 2010 to 2011, women made up just 17.8% of computer science students.

Much consideration has been committed to study the motivation for this drop in female computer science majors. The central ending is that the first personal computers were essentially early making bet systems that securely catered to males. Even though early word processing tools were also available, the marketing explanation told the story of a new device that met the needs of men. As more males began purchasing computers for personal use, the "standard programmer" classification began to take grip in the skilled world of computer science. During the 90's middle, the percentage of women studying computer science at the postsecondary level had fallen to 28 percentages.

Gender Gap in Computing

One of the biggest struggles in front of women in computing in the modern era is that they often find themselves working in an environment that is largely unlikeable, so they don't stay on in the careers in programming and technology. During 2013, a National Public Radio report whispered 40% of computer programmers in the US are female. There is no general consensus for any key reason there are less women in computing. In 2017, James Damore was fired from Google after claiming there was a biological reason for a lack of female computer scientists.

The gender disparity in IT is not worldwide. The ratio of female to male computer scientists is significantly higher in India compared to the West. In Europe, Bulgaria and Romania have the highest rates of women going into computer programming. In government universities in Saudi Arabia in 2014, Arab women made up 59% of students enrolled in computer science. However, the ratio of African American female computer scientists in the US is significantly lower than the national average. It has been suggested there is a greater gap in countries where people of both sexes are treated more equally, contradicting any theories that society in general is to blame for any disparity.

African-American Women in Computer Science

African and American women are among early preparing in computing in the America. Normally, they were borrowed as maths persons to do technical oriented computing needed to support aeronautical and other research works. They included such women as Katherine G. Johnson and Dorothy Vaughan, who had careers of decades at NASA. Among Johnson's projects be calculating the flight path for the United States first mission into space in 1961's. Katherine G is credited as co-writer of 28 scientific papers. The practice in 1960's was to list only the head of the division as author. The crediting of Johnson as an author in a peer-reviewed NASA detailed report is significant.

The Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) was founded in 1947, but computer science developed later as an academic field. Within 1969 Clarence "Skip" Ellis became the first Black man to earn a doctorate degree in computer science. Ten years afterwards, the first Black woman earned a doctorate in computer science.

Why Should Women Want to Work In Computer Science?

Suitable to the advertising strategies of the last three decades, many women have residential misconception about computer science. Whereas the idea of the weed coder is alive and well, many young women may be ignorant of the numerous jobs accessible and the opportunity to make a obvious difference. The University of California at Berkeley experienced a revolution in their introductory computer science classes after changing how they marketed the course.

Even if women now represent 49% of the workforce, as compared to 39% in the 1970's, only 14% of engineers are female. Moreover, the position of female working in computer science and its related professions has gradually declined since the 1990's, dropping from 38% to 23% in the last 20 years. According to the American Association University for Women, convenient are a number of potential steps in the direction of reversing this trend and encouraging more female students to undertake computer science. through promotion an awareness in scientific topics at an premature age or working to eliminate negative connotations and barriers, educators and parents can work together to help girls maintain confidence and curiosity in STEM subjects. In support of professionals previously in the field, women can near to be responsibility models and mentors, though men can take a stand against sexist or discriminatory actions in the workplace.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Nowadays as we stand at the entrance of the 21st century, we are still unable to swank of a society where there is total gender equality or gender impartiality. Until newly, the question of gender equality or sexual category equity is merely a topic of theoretical discussion. Things are varying but rather slowly. For women empowerment I would like to suggest that education is the best weapon for struggle against inequality. Illiteracy is the root of all exploitation, violence and oppression our government make laws for women, try to implement it but also take the care that each and every women in our society should be educated. Lawful awareness to women rights is also necessary and most important thing that women should take care of their rights.

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